

Performance Analysis of Hydroxyl (HHO) Gas Addition on a Gasoline Generator

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ABSTRACT:

The research explores the use of hydroxyl (HHO) gas as a renewable energy source due to the over-reliance on fossil fuels in conventional engines. An HHO cell is designed to produce hydrogen gas used in conventional generators. The cell uses electrolysis of water and potassium hydroxide as a catalyst. The HHO gas is generated with ordinary water without any catalyst and the detailed results of the reaction and analysis are presented. The goal is to develop and test-run an electrolytic cell on a gasoline engine (spark ignition engine) and measure the variation of its parameters in comparison to that of a gasoline engine. The efficiency, performance, power output, and emission are tested under load. This study comprises detailed work on the performance analysis of the HHO cell on the conventional generator, establishes the relationship between the variation of the KOH catalyst against time to produce the HHO gas, the relationship between the variation in voltage and how it directly influences the rate of gas production. Warm water, which is raised above room temperature, is used to verify the above-stated relationships, check if it holds and check the more efficient means of operating the electrolyte based on the temperature of the water used. An increase in the temperature of the water above room temperature leads to more gas production, thereby increasing the efficiency of the HHO cell in gas production. When HHO cell is operated with ordinary water without a catalyst at room temperature, it is observed that the reaction forms a cloudy around the plates of the cell, but the reaction is not turbulent with no significant amount of gas produced, as compared to that of the presence of potassium hydroxide (KOH), which serves as a catalyst to speed up the rate of the reaction and enhance the production of the HHO gas. This clearly shows the need and importance of the presence of a catalyst in the reaction. HHO cell is operated with salt (NaCl) as a catalyst in replacement for potassium hydroxide (KOH) to check the reaction and the rate of gas production. The reaction observed is metal rusting, though it is turbulent a bit more than that of the presence of KOH solution.

Keywords: hydroxyl, electrolyte, generator, gasoline, renewable energy.

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INTRODUCTION

The search for alternative fuels that are renewable, easily obtainable, and can be easily processed to reduce reliance on petroleum and the harmful oxidants released from conventional engines in

order to promote environmentally friendly sources is driven by the problem of global warming and the depletion of fossil fuel reserves. This made researchers concerned about finding more affordable ways to run conventional engines that do not require the use of fossil fuels. One such way is to use hydrogen gas (H_2) as an alternative fuel to increase engine efficiency and provide solutions for the global warming problems.

One of the elements that is most prevalent and appears first on the periodic table is hydrogen and the least expensive ways to produce hydrogen gas is splitting water molecules into hydrogen gas and oxygen gas. This technical concept is known as HHO technology, and it is explored in this study. A compact HHO-generating device can be designed and integrated on a gasoline engine through electrolysis by converting water into hydroxyl (HHO) gas [1]. The HHO technology is still considered rare and developing, but it is very effective in suppressing the use of fossil fuels. The basic material for this technology is water, which has abundant potential in many countries like Nigeria. HHO gas, known as Brown's gas, was named after Professor Yull Brown who was the first to carry out an experiment on HHO gas. HHO gas is the result of electrolysis of water by using a direct electric current, thus splitting water into pure hydrogen and oxygen gas which has a high heating value. The production of HHO gas provides an alternative to conventional fuels reduces overdependence on fossil fuels.

Within the context of advancing previous research on raising awareness about hydrogen production and utilising it as a new fuel to revolutionize the industry and provide an alternative to fossil fuels for internal combustion engine power, the HHO generator, also referred to as a water-powered generator or a hydro cell generator, is considered. A water – fuelled generator can be termed as a device that generates electrical power using water as fuel. Water is an abundantly available renewable energy source, making water-fuelled generator a promising alternative to traditional power sources that rely on non-renewable fossil fuels. These generators use electrolysis, separating water into its two components, hydrogen and oxygen, and use the energy produced to generate electricity. The resulting hydrogen gas can be burned to produce heat and energy, with water vapour being the by-product of the exhaust chamber. Water-fuelled generators have the potential to revolutionize the energy industry by offering a clean, sustainable and cost-effective alternative to traditional power sources.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The history and the development of HHO gas, known as Brown gas, can be broadened down to William Nicholson, who was the first to decompose water in this manner in 1800. In 1960, Yull Brown and Charles Garrett began the research and development of a gas mixture called "Brown's gas". This experiment, which was performed along with Garrett, involves water electrolysis to produce HHO gas, which can be used for various applications.

In the 1970s, Yull Brown made a significant development in his research on using HHO gas for welding and a potential energy source that can also be used for various industrial applications [2]. The scientific community and regulatory bodies did not widely accept the attempt to commercialize HHO gas technology as it was faced with scepticism. Regardless of this, researchers conducted several tests on HHO gas supplementary fuel sources for internal combustion engines, which aims at improving efficiency and reducing the emission of the engines. The potential application of HHO gas is being explored in hydrogen production, fuel cells, and power generation.

Modifying the creation and availability of energy leads to the consideration of improving the conventional generators which run on fossil fuels. Water-fuelled generators, also known as water fuel cells, result from modification of the existing technology and lead to the creation of a power generation system that is more affordable and efficient, increases mobility, lowers fuel consumption, and reduces the release of toxic oxidants into the atmosphere which cause depletion on ozone layers and negatively affect human health. Due to the earlier established advantages of hydrogen gas, an alternative to fossil fuels in internal combustion engines, people are shifting towards fuel-efficient cars. Scientists are exploring alternative fuels, like compressed hydrogen gas for internal combustion engines, which offer increased engine power and reduced pollutants. These aim to improve the engine's efficiency [1].

Hydrogen is the lightest element with an atomic number of 1. It is a colourless, odourless, flammable gas and has several key properties, including a specific gravity of 0.0696 (which explains its robust buoyancy), a boiling point of -253°C (which means that it takes a lot of energy to liquefy hydrogen), and the liquid hydrogen poses some hazards as a cryogenic fluid. It is not on the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) List (which means that it is not generally considered a pollutant); it has a liquid density of 0.08375 kg/m^3 , which means that it is a light liquid [3]. Because of the very low boiling point, a liquid release of hydrogen will rapidly vaporise and very likely not reach the ground in liquid form [4].

Building a system that generates H_2 and integrating it with the generator engine system yields an expensive manufacturing cost and influences the market price. A recommended option is the blending H_2 with natural gas (NG). A recent study showed that the H_2/NG mixture achieved shorter flame development and propagation periods, enhancing combustion efficiency and lowering emission levels.

Natural gas, or methane, is claimed to have a clean substitute in the form of hydrogen. With an estimated 75% of the universe's mass coming from it, it is the most chemical element. Hydrogen atoms are abundant in water, plants, animals, and humans on Earth. According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration, there are two kinds of hydrogen: blue and green. Two primary methods are used to make blue hydrogen from natural gas: steam methane reformation, which produces hydrogen and carbon monoxide at high temperatures and hydrogen production through auto-thermal reformation, which combines methane with steam, oxygen, or CO_2 . When electric electrolyser separates hydrogen from water molecules, green hydrogen is created.

In fuel cells or internal combustion engines, hydrogen is a fuel that may be utilised to carry energy and, when combined with oxygen, essentially emits no greenhouse gases. Water vapour is the sole notable emission. A lot of research is now being done on hydrogen storage and generation. A solar-hydrogen system can give rise to a completely emission-free hydrogen production process. Although steam reformation of methane is now the primary method for producing hydrogen, the emissions involved can be regulated considerably more effectively than with the fuel we use today for transportation. Many people are becoming more aware of the critical problem of climate change. The global warming phenomena has been directly caused by rising CO_2 levels [5].

According to the Southwest Research Institute (SWRI), San Antonio, Texas, USA, hydrogen has a higher energy density than conventional internal combustion fuels when compressed. It has a high auto-ignition temperature compared to gasoline and diesel fuels. When hydrogen combines with oxygen to produce electricity, which in turn powers electric motors. This process is known as electrochemical conversion and occurs in hydrogen fuel cells. As shown in Table 1, many ways exist to manufacture and transform hydrogen, an energy carrier, into energy. The most environmentally friendly method for producing hydrogen is the electrolysis of water. The benefits of this hypothetical hydrogen economy are contingent on using clean, renewable energy sources as electricity. One example is that power is used along main paths to usable hydrogen gas. It is only possible to produce hydrogen by emitting emissions once there is a significant move towards renewable energy [5]

Table 1. Various Methods to Produce Hydrogen

Method	Process	Implementation
Stream reforming of methane gas	In the presence of nickel catalyst & at $700-110^{\circ}\text{C}$ $\text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ Next reaction at a lower temperature	Current major source of hydrogen
Hydrogen gas from coal (gasification)	At high temperature and pressure $\text{Coal} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2(\text{g})$ $\text{Syngas} = \text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4$	Current method of mass hydrogen production
Electrolysis of water	An electric current passing through water $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2(\text{g}) + \text{O}_2(\text{g})$	Not in widespread use due to cost of electricity
Solar -Hydrogen system	An electric current passing through water $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2(\text{g}) + \text{O}_2(\text{g})$	Not in widespread use due to cost of renewable energy sources

Source: Chamousis, 2009

Several factors affect the production of HHO gas. These includes voltage, current, temperature, the number of plates and the catalyst, as explained below:

- **Voltage:** Increasing the applied voltage across the electrodes in the HHO cell generator will increase the efficiency of the cell and enhance the electrolysis process. The higher the voltage, the more electrical energy to drive the splitting of water molecules which result to an increase in the gas molecules. This is in accordance with Faraday's law of electrolysis which states "that the amount of substance produced in an electrolysis reaction is directly proportional to the amount of electrical charge passed through the cell". Higher voltage results in a greater quantity of HHO gas produced in a given time [6].
- **Current:** The rate of HHO gas production is directly proportional to the current passing through the electrolysis cell. Higher current results in a faster rate of HHO gas generation. Faraday's law of electrolysis states; that the mass of a substance produced during electrolysis is directly proportional to the quantity of electricity passed through the cell. Increasing the current will yield an increase in the total electrical charge delivered, which will lead to more HHO gas production. More current yields a greater volume of HHO gas in a given amount of time [7].
- **Number of plates:** The number of plates will affect the efficiency and the rate of HHO gas being produced. It will directly impact the gas production. The more the plates the more HHO gas produced. Reduction in the number of plates will results in low HHO gas to be produced.
- **Reduction in gas production:** This will lead to a reduction in the surface area available for electrolysis.
- **Slower gas production:** With fewer plates, the rate at which HHO gas is generated will decrease.
- **Effect of water temperature:** The electrolysis process is much more efficient at higher solution temperatures because the ionic conductivity and surface reaction of an electrolyte increase with the temperature which is due to the thermodynamic behaviour of a water molecule, as its splitting reaction accelerates with temperature.

Considering the relationship between voltage and current in the HHO generator, the voltage applied across the electrodes determines the potential difference (PD) and the current is the rate of electron flow. Voltage and current need to be regulated to optimize gas production while maintaining the safety of equipment [8]. The size and spacing of the electrodes in the cell also affect the relationship between the voltage, current and gas production. Therefore, there is a need for proper electrode design and spacing. To verify this theory, the experiment was conducted with water at 80°C and compared HHO gas production with atmospheric temperature. It is observed that the rise of HHO gas is significant at lower molarity and substantial difference observed with NaOH use as a catalyst [9].

Two kinds of fuel cells can be employed in HHO generator designs. These are called dry cells and wet cells. The benefits of the HHO gas generator are significant and consistent in gas production. Using wet cells has the drawback of increasing internal heat generation and necessitating a larger current (ampere). The wet fuel cell causes more electrode corrosion than the dry fuel cell because of the larger plate exposed surface to the electrolyte. Wet cells produce more HHO gas than dry cells for the same design parameters because all of their electrodes are submerged in the electrolyte solution, according to a recent study comparing the production rates of HHO using dry and wet cells with different plate configurations. Most of the electrodes in a dry cell HHO gas generator are not buried in the electrolyte. Only the space between the electrodes is filled with electrolyte. Dry cell HHO generators have the following benefits: waterless electrolysis, in which only water is trapped between the cell plates; less heat creation from hot and cold water circulation inside the generator; and reduced electric current consumption since less heat is produced from the energy [10].

Yilmaz studied the effect of HHO addition on compression ignition engines; their results reported an increase in engine torque by an average of 19.1%, a reduction in CO and hydrocarbons (HC) emissions, and specific fuel consumption (SFC) by averages of 13.5%, 5%, and 14%, respectively [11]. Studies have also shown the effect of H₂ enrichment on a spark ignition methanol-fuelled

engine, and reported an increase in brake mean effective pressure (bmep) and both the thermal and volumetric efficiencies, with 3% of H₂ by volume of the intake air [12].

Hydrogen gas is an alternative fuel for internal combustion engines (ICEs). It reduces the cost of fossil fuels and the environmental hazards caused by conventional engines. Hydro oxygen generator (HHO cell) is one of the means of achieving this through the electrolysis of water by separating water to its molecules through the use of a catalyst to speed up the rate of the reaction along with DC current passing through the poles of the electrolytic cell.

In this current research, an HHO cell is constructed to generate the HHO gas used to power a conventional generator. Analysis of voltage applied, quantity of catalyst present in the electrolytic solution and temperature of water is done during the production of HHO gas.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials and Equipment Used

Selection of materials for the current study was based on the materials that help to achieve the aim of the study. The following materials and equipment are utilised:

1. **Stainless steel plate:** The 304L stainless steel plate as shown in Plate 1, was selected for the current research due to its properties:

- High corrosion resistance: Since the plates will be immersed in an alkaline solution, a material that can withstand corrosion i.e it doesn't get stained, is needed.
- Temperature resistant: Stainless steel plates are said to be able to withstand temperature compared to other non-corrosive materials.
- Conductivity: Stainless steel has the ability to conduct electricity.
- Low maintenance: Stainless steel plates require less maintenance than other metals or steel. This property of stainless steel is very important in this study as the plates are fully immersed in an alkaline solution throughout the period of operation.
- Cost: Stainless steel of 316L and 304L can be used. For this research, stainless steel 304L of 2mm thickness was used.
- The material has high tensile strength and easy to fabricate.

The detailed properties of the stainless-steel plates used in this current research are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Detailed Properties of Stainless-Steel Plate

PROPERTIES	VALUE
Density (x1000 Kg/m ³)	8
Poisson' ratio	0.27 – 0.30
Elastic modulus (Gpa)	193
Tensile strength (Mpa)	515
Yield strength (Mpa)	205
Elongation (%)	40
Reduction in area (%)	50
Hardness (HRB)	88
Thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ / °C)	17.2
Thermal conductivity (W/m)	16.2

Source: Bambhania et al., 2020

2. **Filter bottles:** The filter bottles as shown in Plate 2, were used in this research since the electrolytic chamber is required to withstand up to pressure of 8 bar due to the reaction that will take place inside it and the HHO gas that will be generated inside the electrolytic chamber is explosive. Therefore, there is a need to use a chamber that can withstand the pressure. The transparency of the filter bottle container in which the reaction in the chamber can be monitored and proper observation of the process can be noted. Two bar filters were set up for this reaction in this study.
3. **Stainless steel rod:** Plate 3 shows the stainless-steel rods used. This was use due to the above stated properties of stainless-steel plate. The dimension of the stainless-steel rod used was M10.
6. **Nuts and washers:** Plates 4 and 5 show the nuts and washers used in the study. Both nuts and washers are made from stainless steel and possess the earlier stated properties of stainless steel.
4. **Catalyst (KOH):** In this study, potassium chloride (KOH), also known as caustic potash, as shown in Plate 6, was selected as the electrolyte because it is a strong base and it easily absorbs water vapour. KOH has a high solubility in water up to 1100g/L (principle of HHO generator).
5. **Battery:** A battery that can supply a voltage of not less than 12 volts and a current of 10 amperes was used to supply voltage across the poles of the rods (anode and cathode) and current, which will create the reaction in the immersed alkaline solution. The Plate 7 shows the battery used in this current study.
6. **A working IC gasoline generator:** The hydrogen cell generator is to be fitted to an existing gasoline generator (Plate 8) by removing the gasoline fuel tank and replacing it with the HHO cell generator for test runs and other observations.
7. **Plastic washers:** Plate 9 shows the plastic washers used. The plastic washers serve as the spacer and insulator, which separate the plates from getting into contact with the rod in the cell.
8. **Plastic and Copper Fittings:** The fittings were selected to collect the HHO gas from the chamber at a control rate, which is reduce in volume by the reduction in the size of the fittings, then to the hose and to the engine carburettor before entering the combustion chamber. Plate 10 shows the fittings used in this study.
9. **Tapper:** The tapper was selected to seal the mouth of the fittings when fitted together, thereby avoiding gas leakage.
10. **ON/Off switch:** This switch controls the flow of electric charge from the battery to the cell.
11. **Purified distilled water:** Clean water is needed in its purest form to ensure the reaction is not contaminated or affected by impurities.

Plate 1. 304L Stainless Steel

Plate 2. Filter Bottles

Plate 3. Threaded Stainless-Steel Studs

Plate 4. Nuts

Plate 5. Washers

Plate 6. Potassium Hydroxide (KOH)

Plate 7. 12-Volt Battery

Plate 8. Generator

Plate 9. Plastic Washers

Plate 10. Plastic and Copper Fittings

Experimental Method and Procedure

The 304 stainless steel sheet of 2mm thickness was cut into 12 pieces; each plate is 50mm by 40mm in dimension and two holes were made in each plate in which the drilling bit of 10mm diameter was

used to make the first hole and the drilling bit of 12mm diameter was used to make the second hole, as shown in Plate11. This was done to ensure that the arrangements of the plates in the steel rod were achieved correctly. The steel plates were cut and drilled in the Mechanical Workshop, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

The surface area of each plate cut out from the 304 stainless steel sheet of 2mm thickness was ground with sandpaper to remove surface particles (dirt), aid the good reaction of the steel in the electrolyser to increase the surface area of each plate, aid more production, and avoid contamination that can affect the rate of the reaction (slow or fast).

Plate 11. Separators on Stainless Steel Rods

The filter bottles were brought to the workshop for drilling and cutting off the restrictions in the head cover to fit into the research. In the process of cutting the restrictions in the filter bar cover, a hot knife was used by dipping it into the fire and melting the restriction parts of the cover to be fit for the use and purpose of the research. Two holes of the plates' hole dimensions were drilled at the top of the filter bottle, as shown in Plate 12 in which the threaded bolts passed as the electrodes in electrolyser.

Plate 12. Filter Bottle Cover

The filter bottle can withstand a pressure of up to 8 bar and the drilled filter bottle serves as the electrolyser chamber where the reaction takes place. The second filter bottle contains clean and

purified water connected mouth to mouth with the electrolyte chamber (filter bottle) through fittings (1-inch plug) and the other side of the water filter bottle was fit with some other inches (1-inch nipple, inch by 34 elbow, 24 inch nipple, 34 by 12 elbow) this served as a passage for the HHO gas collected over water through the hose to reach the engine carburettor.

As a means to achieve the insulation of the bolts from one plate and get it in contact with the other, each plate was only in contact with one plate at a time; a plastic washer was used to achieve it. To achieve this, plastic covers were cut out to serve as plastic washers in this case. However, because plastic washers were not in the market, another method was devised by cutting bottle covers in shape of the washers to achieve the purpose of the plastic washers. About 90 pieces of it were made.

The plastic washers served as the spacer and insulator, separating the plates from contact with the rod and the washers used in the cell. This makes it easy to achieve the anode and cathode separation, which are the poles in the cell.

Arrangement of the plates on the rods

The stainless-steel plates were arranged on the stainless-steel rods, as shown in Plate 13, which serves as the electrodes (anode and cathode). The order of arrangement is in such a way that the steel plates are in contact with the steel rod in one part and the other side of the plates are separated by the plastic washers. The arrangement is as follows:

First rod → nut, plastic washer, then the steel plate.

Second rod → nut, then the stainless-steel plate.

Plate 13. Arrangement of Plates on the Steel Rods

The arrangement of the plates on the steel rods, known as the poles of the cells, was tested one after the other to ensure that each plate only had one contact with the rods at one side, and plastic washers separated the other side. Throughout the process, a digital meter that reads ohms, the resistance of each plate, was used. At the final stage of the plate arrangement, the plates were properly checked against any partial contact with the poles at a time.

Chemical reactions in the electrolysis

In the alkaline solution, at the negatively charged cathode, a reduction reaction takes place with electrons (e^-) from the cathode being liberated to hydrogen cations to form hydrogen gas (the half-reaction balanced with acid).

Reduction at cathode:

An oxidation reaction occurs at the positively charged anode, generating oxygen gas and giving electrons to the anode to complete.

Oxidation at the Anode:

The balanced half-reaction:

Combining the two-half reaction pair yields the overall decomposition of water into oxygen and hydrogen.

Overall reaction:

From the above reaction, it is deduced that the number of hydrogen molecules produced is twice that of oxygen molecules. At the same temperature and pressure of both gases, the volume of hydrogen gas will double that of oxygen gas produced.

Installation process

The HHO cell installation process is designed to generate HHO gas, which will be passed to the engine carburettor to atomize and then to the combustion chamber for smooth and perfect combustion. The design of the cell is shown below:

Plate 14. Cell

Cell A, as shown in Plate 14, houses the stainless-steel plates arranged on the rods (electrodes) to form the cathode and anode in the cell. Cell A was filled with an alkaline solution of KOH + water (H_2O) to serve as the electrolyte solution in the cell. The cell was filled to the top of the last plate on the electrode to ensure that all the plates were immersed in the solution for uniform generation of hydrogen gas (H^{2+}).

Cell B houses the distilled water only in which a pipe connected to the hole links to cell A, where the proper reaction takes place. The hose was inserted to evenly transfer the reaction in cell A to the distilled water in cell B by creating bubbles inside it in which the pure gas (H_2) produced, then

combined with the O₂ collected over the distilled water, was forced to pass through the hole at the other side of the chamber which as a hose attached to it link to the engine carburettor. The process was sealed to facilitate the perfect gas collection and avoid leakages in the joining.

The filter bar, which is cell A, is where the reaction takes place. The poles were connected to a DC supply of a battery of 12 volts and 10 amps, in which the reaction immediately built up and it was then passed to cell B, as stated earlier. For compartment and mobility of the generator the cell can be fixed to the generator chassis, in which both can be moved together at once.

A voltage and current regulator was incorporated with the cell to monitor the voltage and current from the source (battery) delivered to the poles of the cell to control and check for variation in the current and voltage delivered or for the need to increase the voltage or current at any time. The variation in current and voltage supplied to poles will directly affect gas production. Therefore, the battery delivers a constant current and voltage over the period of operation of the engine.

Design Analysis

Mathematical analysis of the HHO cell

The dimensions of the plates are 4 cm in length, 5 cm in breadth and 2 mm thick.

Hole drill diameters on the plate are 10 mm for the small hole and 12 mm for the big hole

Number of the plates used is 12

Dimensions for the Rod used: Length = 31 cm, diameter = 10 mm, number of rods = 2

Terminal cable (wire): Length = 71cm and diameter = 1.5 mm = 0.15 cm

Nuts and washers: Number used = 32

The diameter of each nut and washer = 12 mm.

The equation provided below is important for calculating the resistance of the cell arrangement:

$$R_T = R_p + R_{rods} + R_{wire} + R_{nuts+washer} \quad (4)$$

Recall;

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{A} \quad (5)$$

where

R is the resistance

L is the length

A is the area

ρ is the resistivity of the conducting material.

Mathematical analysis of stainless-steel plate

Resistivity of steel (ρ) = 70 $\mu\Omega\text{cm}$ = $(70 \times 10^{-6}) \Omega\text{cm}$ = $7 \times 10^{-5} \Omega\text{cm}$

Length (L) of the plate used = 5 cm

Breadth (B) of the plate used = 4 cm

Hole diameters = 1cm for the small hole and 1.2 cm for the big hole

Area of the rectangular plate = $L \times B = 5 \times 4 = 20 \text{ cm}^2$

Area of the holes in the rectangular plate; $A = \pi r^2$

1st hole, diameter = 1cm

$$\text{Area (A)} = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = 3.142 \times (10 \times 10^{-1})^2 \times \frac{1}{4} = 3.142 \text{ cm}^2$$

2nd hole; diameter = 1.2 cm

$$\text{Area (A)} = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = 3.142 \times (12 \times 10^{-1})^2 \times \frac{1}{4} = 4.524 \text{ cm}^2$$

The surface area exposes to H₂ in the solution is given as = area of the rectangular plate – the hole areas.

$$\text{Surface area of H}_2 = 20 - (3.142 + 4.524) = 12.33 \text{ cm}^2$$

Twelve plates are arranged in the cell: total area exposes to the H₂ in the cell is given as (12×12.33) cm² = 147.96 cm².

The length of the terminal cable used is 71cm on each side from the positive and negative terminals of the battery to the electrodes. 71cm × 2 = 142 cm

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{A}$$

$$R = 7 \times 10^{-5} \times \frac{5}{12.33} = 2.8 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$$

For the 12 plates arranged in the cell, the total resistance offered by the plates is given as follows:

$$12 \times 2.8 \times 10^{-5} \Omega = 3.4 \times 10^{-4} \Omega$$

Total resistance of the plates = 3.4×10⁻⁴ Ω

Rods (electrodes)

$$\text{Resistance of the electrode (R}_{\text{rods}}) = \frac{\rho L}{A}$$

Diameter of electrode = 10 mm = 1 cm

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = \frac{3.142 \times 1^2}{4} = 0.7855 \text{ cm}^2$$

Resistivity of the stainless-steel rod (ρ) = 7 × 10⁻⁵ Ωm

Length (l) = 31 cm = 31 × 10 mm = 310 mm

$$\text{Resistance of rod} = \frac{7 \times 10^{-5} \times 31}{0.7855} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3} \Omega$$

Total resistance of the rod = 2×2.8×10⁻³ Ω = 5.6× 10⁻³ Ω

Terminal cable (wire)

$$\text{Resistance of the terminal wire used (R}_w) = \frac{\rho L}{A}$$

Resistivity of the wire (ρ_w) = 1.72 × 10⁻⁸ Ω m = 1.72 × 10⁻⁶ Ω cm

Length of the wire = 71 cm = 710 mm

$$\text{Area of the wire} = A = \frac{3.142 \times 0.15^2}{4} = 0.017674 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$\text{Resistance of wire} = \frac{1.72 \times 10^{-6} \times 71}{0.017674} = 6.9 \times 10^{-3} \Omega$$

Total resistance of the wire = 6.9×10⁻³ Ω

Nuts

Resistance of the nuts (R_{nuts}) arranged in parallel

$$(R_{nuts}) = \frac{\rho_{ss}L}{A}$$

where

ρ_{ss} is the resistivity of stainless steel

Length (l) = thickness = 5mm = 0.5 cm

Diameter of the nut = 12 mm = 1.2 cm

$$\text{Area of nut} = A = \frac{3.142 \times (12 \times 10^{-1})^2}{4} = 1.13112 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$R_n = \frac{7 \times 10^{-5} \times 0.5}{1.13112} = 3.09 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$$

$$R_{nut} = \frac{1}{r} = \frac{1}{3.09 \times 10^{-5}} = 32362.46 \Omega$$

Since 32 nuts were used, therefore,

$$\text{Total resistance of the nuts } (R_{nuts}) = (32 \times 32362.46) \Omega = 1.04 \times 10^6 \Omega$$

Washers

$$\text{Resistance of the stainless-steel washers } (R_{washer}) = \frac{\rho_{washer} \times L}{A}$$

Length (l) = thickness of the washer = 2mm = 0.2 cm

Diameter of the washer = 12 mm = 1.2 cm

$$\text{Area of washer} = A = \frac{3.142 \times (12 \times 10^{-1})^2}{4} = 1.13112 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$R_{washer} = \frac{7 \times 10^{-5} \times 0.2}{1.13112} = 1.24 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$$

For parallel arrangement of the washers in the HHO cell;

$$R = \frac{1}{1.24 \times 10^{-5}} = 80645.2 \Omega$$

In the HHO CELL 34 stainless steel washers were used.

$$\text{Total resistance of washer } R_{washer} = 34 \times 80645.2 \Omega = 2580646 \Omega$$

Neglecting the resistance of the plastic washers, the overall resistance of the HHO cell designed is the addition of all the resistance calculated.

$$R_T = R_p + R_{rods} + R_{wire} + R_{nuts+washer}$$

$$R_T = (3.4 \times 10^{-4}) + (5.6 \times 10^{-3}) + (6.9 \times 10^{-3}) + (1.04 \times 10^6) + (2580646)$$

$$R_T = 3620646.4 \Omega$$

The typical Gibbs free energy of 237 kJ of electrical energy is needed to dissociate one mole of water into its constituents, hydrogen and oxygen.

Voltage = Current x Resistance

Voltage applied = 12 volts

$$V = IR \quad (6)$$

$$I = \frac{V}{R} = \frac{12}{3620646.4} = 3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ amps}$$

Power of the HHO cell = $IV = 3.3 \times 10^{-6} \times 12 = 3.96 \times 10^{-5}$ watts

For the battery used to power the cell;

Battery voltage = 12.4 volts

Current (I) per hour = $75\text{Ah} = \frac{75}{60} = 1.25$ amps/min

The battery used is supplying 1.25 amps/min

Battery power = $IV = 1.25 \times 12.4 = 15.5$ watts

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of different operational conditions of the HHO Cell

The HHO cell gas generator was operated with water at normal room temperature (25°C) and mixed with a strong alkaline (that is, potassium hydroxide also known as caustic potash (KOH)).

The results obtained from the investigations are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Addition of KOH with Water at Room Temperature

Potassium hydroxide (KOH) addition (g)	Time Taken (s)		$\frac{t_1+t_2}{2}$ (s)
	t_1	t_2	
20	87.19	59.81	73.50
30	78.89	61.87	70.38
40	63.74	68.46	66.10
50	90.32	78.20	84.26

The volume of HHO gas produced is kept constant and the quantity of KOH addition is varied to determine the time taken to fill the 75-cl bottle (0.75 litres). This gives the relationship between the quantities of KOH addition in the alkaline solution and the time taken to produce 0.75 litres of HHO gas. The graph of potassium hydroxide (KOH) added against the time taken for the HHO gas to fill the 0.75-litre bottle is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Time Taken for the Production of HHO Gas Against KOH

The following observations are obtained during the investigations:

- a. It is revealed that after every reading, the voltage supplied by the battery decreases slightly due to the inability to recharge it during operation. A mean battery voltage of 12.1 volts is obtained for the experiment and the graph is shown in Figure 1.
- b. As shown in Figure 1, the time taken for the HHO cell to fill a bottle of 0.75 litres reduces as the concentration of the potassium hydroxide in the water solution increases, considering the first three specimens of the KOH (20g, 30g, 40g). Therefore, it can be deduced that the time taken to produce HHO gas is inversely proportional to the grams of potassium hydroxide present in the alkaline solution for the first three specimens.
- c. For the 50g of potassium hydroxide (KOH) in the alkaline solution, it is observed that the time taken for the hydrogen gas to fill the 0.75 litres increases, as shown in Figure 1 and the graph takes a sharp curve upward, which does not follow the relationship drawn out in the first three specimens of potassium hydroxide (KOH). This increase in time occurs due to the reduction in the battery voltage when taking the readings. Voltage drops directly influences the time taken for the hydrogen gas production.

The below conditions of the cell are met during the current investigations:

1. Constant voltage and current supplied.
2. The number of plates is the same.
3. The volume of HHO gas is expected to be constant.
4. The temperature of water and other elements is kept constant.

$$m = Q \times \rho \quad (7)$$

where m = HHO gas production rate or flow rate (kg/s),

Q = HHO gas discharge (m³/s),

ρ = HHO density (kg/m³).

Density of HHO gas (ρ_{HHO}) = 0.54kg/m³ = 0.54 kg/(1x10⁻⁶) = 540000kg/cm³

$$Q_{\text{HHO}} = \frac{V_{\text{HHO}}}{t} \quad (8)$$

where;

Q_{HHO} = HHO gas production rate (ml/s),

V_{HHO} gas = HHO gas volume (ml),

t = Time required to produce HHO gas (s).

Voltage Against the Rate of Gas Production

Table 4 shows the data obtained during the voltage variation against the rate of HHO gas produced using a constant measurement of 0.75 litres of HHO gas produced against the time taken. The gas production rate is obtained by dividing 0.75 litres by the mean time taken for each stage of applied voltage. The potassium hydroxide (KOH) is kept constant at 40g during the voltage variation.

Table 4. Voltage Variation Against the Rate of HHO Gas Produced

Voltage applied (V)	Time (s)	Rate of gas production (Litre / seconds)	Mass flow rate $M = Q \times \rho_{\text{HHO}}$ (kg/s)
12.3	73.50	$\frac{0.75}{73.50} = 0.0102$	$\frac{0.0102}{540000} = 1.89 \times 10^{-8}$
12.1	68.18	$\frac{0.75}{68.18} = 0.0110$	$\frac{0.0110}{540000} = 2.04 \times 10^{-8}$
11.9	70.09	$\frac{0.75}{70.09} = 0.0107$	$\frac{0.0107}{540000} = 1.98 \times 10^{-8}$
11.6	84.26	$\frac{0.75}{84.26} = 0.0089$	$\frac{0.0089}{540000} = 1.64 \times 10^{-8}$

Figure 2. Gas Production Rate against Voltage

The graph of voltage against rate of gas production is shown in the Figure 2. The following points are observed:

- As shown in Figure 2, the gas production rate is directly proportional to the voltage applied across the pole of the HHO cell.
- The gas production rate and voltage increase linearly from 11.6 to 12.1 volts. The graph slightly changes from a linear graph to a curve from 12.1 to 12.3 volts. A further increase in the voltage supplied across the poles of the HHO cell above 12.0 volts will only slightly increase the gas production rate compared to when the voltage is 11.6.
- At high temperature, the HHO cell generates more heat and the temperature increases, thereby creating more loss which slows down the rate of the gas production when the voltage is high.
- Table 4 shows the same mass flow rate was obtained for all the investigations. This shows a relationship such that the change in voltage applied is directly proportional to the gas production rate while the mass flow rate for a specific range of voltage does not change. That is, the mass flow rate remains almost constant ($2.00 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Kg/s}$) throughout each investigation.

The mass flow rate of HHO gas for the quantity of gas produced for the different investigations is calculated using the relation below:

$$M = Q \times \rho$$

For 20g of KOH at 0.75 litres

$$\text{Mass flow rate} = \frac{0.0102 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}}{540000 \text{ Kg}/\text{cm}^3} = 1.89 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Kg}/\text{s} \approx 2.00 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Kg}/\text{s}$$

HHO Cell Analysis when Operated with Warm Water Above Room Temperature

Operating the HHO cell with warm water (above room temperature) and potassium hydroxide (KOH). It is stated that an increase in the temperature of water will cause the gas molecules to gain energy and move more rapidly this results in increase in water volume. It is clearly observed that:

a. A decrease in the temperature of the water will cause the water molecules to be held together (ice) and have a definite volume while an increase in the temperature of the water will break the water molecules (hydrogen and oxygen) to move freely, therefore the state of the water changes to steam (gas).

An increase in the temperature of the water will lead to more gas production, thereby increasing the efficiency of the HHO cell in terms of gas production.

b. It requires more energy, the system gets hotter, and more energy loss occurs compared to when operated with water at room temperature.

Table 5 shows the data obtained when the HHO cell is operated with warm water above the room temperature along with KOH addition:

Table 5. HHO Cell Operated with Warm Water

Potassium hydroxide (KOH) addition (g)	Time Taken (s)		$\frac{t_1+t_2}{2}$ (s)
	t ₁	t ₂	
20	49.19	35.59	42.39
30	37.52	34.74	36.13
40	35.98	33.80	34.89
50	29.61	30.35	29.98

The HHO cell is operated under a mean voltage of 12.1 volts and the data in Table 4 are obtained against the variation of KOH addition. The measurement of the volume of HHO gas produced is kept constant at 0.75 litres, the same as the HHO cell with water at room temperature.

Figure 3. Time Taken Against KOH in Warm Water

The graph of time taken against potassium hydroxide in warm water is shown in the Figure 3. The following observations are obtained during the investigations:

a. It is observed that using warm water in the operation of the HHO cell leads to a lower time in the production of HHO gas using the same measurement of 0.75 litres used for water at room temperature. This can be attributed to the warm water's effect, which speeds up the reaction and increases gas production against time taken.

- b. The graph also follows the relation established earlier in Figure 1 of water at room temperature; time taken is inversely proportional to the rate of KOH addition.
- c. As shown in Figure 3, the time it takes for the HHO cell to fill the 0.75-litre bottle only slightly changes between 30g and 40g of KOH addition.
- d. Between 20g and 40g, it forms a linear graph showing the gradual decrease in the time taken compared to the graph of time taken against time against KOH at room temperature in Figure 1.

The above observations are based on the under-listed conditions of the HHO cell

1. Constant voltage and current supplied.
2. The number of plates is the same.
3. The volume of HHO gas is expected to be constant.
4. The temperature of water and other elements is kept constant.

Voltage Against Rate of Gas Production by Keeping the Catalyst KOH at 40g

Table 6 shows the data obtained when the voltage varied at a constant 40g of hydrogen hydroxide when the HHO cell was operated with warm water.

Table 6. Voltage against Gas Production Rate (Warm Water)

Voltage applied (volts)	Time taken (s)	Rate of gas production (litre / secs)	Mass flow rate $M = Q \times \rho_{\text{hho}}$ (kg/s)
12.3	30.61	$\frac{0.75}{30.61} = 0.0245$	$\frac{0.0245}{540000} = 5.54 \times 10^{-8}$
12.0	32.62	$\frac{0.75}{32.61} = 0.0230$	$\frac{0.0230}{540000} = 4.26 \times 10^{-8}$
11.9	34.46	$\frac{0.75}{34.46} = 0.0217$	$\frac{0.0217}{540000} = 4.02 \times 10^{-8}$
11.8	41.89	$\frac{0.75}{41.89} = 0.0179$	$\frac{0.0179}{540000} = 3.31 \times 10^{-8}$

The HHO cell is operated when the voltage is varied between 12.3 and 11.8 volts at constant 40g of potassium hydroxide addition. Figure 4 shows the rate of gas production as the voltage varies and HHO is operated with warm water.

Figure 4. Voltage Against Rate of HHO Gas Production Using Warm Water

The observations obtained during the investigations are shown in Figure 4. As it is earlier stated that an increase in the temperature of water causes the gas molecules to gain energy and move more rapidly and increases the water volume. It is clearly observed that:

- It conforms with the observation deduced from the graph of voltage against the rate of gas production of the HHO cell with normal water at room temperature. That is, an increase in voltage leads to an increase in the rate of HHO gas production per second.
- From Table 6 above, the mass flow rate of HHO gas obtained results in a slight difference, which is said to be affected by the variation in the voltage applied within a short time taken. Unlike the earlier results obtained for water at room temperature, the mass flow rate is affected by the temperature of water used, which results in a slight difference in the results over a long time taken.
- At the battery's 12.0 and 11.9 voltages, the mass flow rate is said to be almost the same. This might be due to the slight difference in the voltage applied, which is very close.
- Figure 5 shows the graph of the mass flow rate against the rate of gas production. The graph reveals that the mass flow rate is directly proportional to the mass flow rate.

Figure 5. Mass Flow Rate Against Rate of Gas Production Using Warm Water

HHO Cell Operated with Ordinary Water at Room Temperature Without the Addition of a Catalyst

In the operation of the HHO cell, ordinary water is used at room temperature with no catalyst added. It is observed that the reaction form is cloudy around the plates of the cell, but the reaction is not turbulent, and no significant amount of gas is produced, as that of the presence of potassium hydroxide (KOH), which serves as a catalyst to speed up the rate of the reaction and enhance the production of the HHO gas. This clearly shows the need and importance of the presence of a catalyst in the reaction.

HHO Cell Operated with Table Salt (NaCl)

The HHO cell is operated with salt (NaCl) as a catalyst in replacement for potassium hydroxide (KOH) to check the reaction and the rate of gas produced and ensure the operation of the cell is safe. In the operation of the HHO cell which contains water and salt (NaCl) as its electrolyte, the reaction observed is metal rusting, though it is turbulent a bit more than that of the presence of KOH solution. The reaction is set to wash out the stainless-steel plates in the cell and bubbles form around the plates with a change in the colour of the electrolyte. The picture on plate 15 shows the reaction that occurs in the HHO cell.

Plate 15. Reaction in HHO Cell using NaCl as a Catalyst

CONCLUSIONS

This research has been carried out to reduce over-reliance on fossil fuels to power conventional generators by producing an HHO gas. An HHO cell is designed to use electrolysis of water and potassium hydroxide as a catalyst. The HHO gas produced powers a conventional generator and works for five minutes. This study comprises detailed work on the performance analysis of the HHO cell on the conventional generator, establishes the relationship between the variation of the potassium hydroxide (KOH) catalyst against time to produce the HHO gas, the relationship between the variation in voltage and how it directly influences the rate of gas production. Warm water is used in the HHO cell, and the results are compared with room-temperature water. Increasing the water temperature above room temperature leads to more gas production, thereby increasing the efficiency of the HHO cell in gas production. When the HHO cell is operated with ordinary water without a catalyst at room temperature, it is observed that a cloudy reaction forms around the plates of the cell, but the reaction is not turbulent with no significant amount of gas produced, as that of the presence of potassium hydroxide (KOH), which serves as a catalyst to speed up the rate of the reaction and enhance the production of the HHO gas. This clearly shows the need and importance of the presence of a catalyst in the reaction. This current research has revealed that a conventional generator can be powered using HHO gas. Also, the need to recharge the battery is revealed when the HHO gas is produced, as the conventional generator goes off when the voltage is reduced.

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